
Implementing Industry 4.0 Principles

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Abstract. This article identifies the advances, advantages, limitations, requirements and current methodologies in implementing the strategic Industry 4.0 (I4.0) initiative. It focuses on all research works, mainly production planning. To do so, it proposes a classification of the principles of I4.0 design terms that contemplates the following classification aspects: interconnection/connectivity, decentralised decision making, technical assistance, the human factor, intelligence/awareness, interoperability, information transparency, technology, organisation, conceptual frameworks and production planning. It also presents the models, algorithms, heuristics and metaheuristics of the components used in relation to an I4.0 setting. Finally, a considerable number of reference conceptual frameworks is analysed, which allow the term I4.0 to be defined. It is worth stressing that no literature review has been identified to date that considers enablers on the whole and focuses on planning production in the I4.0 context, but has instead searched for bibliographic information by collecting the enablers that each author has considered belong to I4.0. So, to date, no work is found on the state of the art in which enablers take an I4.0 approach.

Key words: Digital manufacturing, industry 4.0, smart factory, production planning.

List of acronyms

3DP	3 Dimensional printing
AFMS	Automated flow-shop manufacturing system
AHP	Analytic hierarchy process
AR	Augmented reality
BPMN	Business process model and notation
CAutoD	Computer automated design
CBM	Cloud-based manufacturing
CPPS	Cyber-physical production system
CPS	Cyber-physical system
DDS	Data distribution service
DT	Digital twin

DTaaS	Digital twin as a service
ERP	Enterprise resources planning
EIS	Enterprise information system
FAHP	Fuzzy analytic hierarchy process
GPS	Global positioning system
HDM	Head mounted device
HiTraP-AT	Hierarchical transition planner for automation technology
I1.0	Industry 1.0
I4.0	Industry 4.0
I4PML	Industry 4.0 modelling language
I4PMM	Industry 4.0 modelling method
I4SEA	Industry 4.0 service enabler architecture
IAR	Industrial augmented reality
ICT	Information and communication technologies
IIoT	Industrial Internet of things
IIRA	Industrial Internet reference framework
IM	Intelligent manufacturing
IoS	Internet of services
IoT	Internet of things
IPM	Industrial processes monitoring
IS	Information system
IWNs	Industrial wireless networks
IWS	Industrial wearable system
LLRU	Locally-aware least recently used
MCPS	Manufacturing CPS
MES	Manufacturing execution system
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OEE	Overall equipment effectiveness
OPC	Optimum programme control
OPC UA	Open platform communications unified architecture
PLM	Product lifecycle management
PON	Passive optical access network
PPC	Production planning and control
RAMI 4.0	Report reference architecture model Industrie 4.0
RFID	Radio frequency identification
RMS	Reconfigurable manufacturing system
SCPS	Social cyber-physical system
SDCM	Software-defined cloud manufacturing
SDN	Software defined networking
SM	Smart manufacturing

SME	Small- and medium-sized enterprise
SOMS	Self-organising manufacturing system
SOPHOS-MS	SOPHOS manufacturing system
TSN	Time sensitive networking
UML	Unified modelling language
UX	User experience
VLE	Virtual learning education
VR	Virtual reality
WNs	Wireless networks
WoS	Web of Science

1 Introduction

Digital manufacturing refers to a manufacturing process which, with the support of technologies such as virtual reality (VR), computer networks, rapid prototyping and database, is based on customer demand so as to analyse, organise and recombine product information, process information and resource information, implement product design and function simulation as well as rapid prototyping, and then perform rapid production to meet customer demand and quality standards (Zhou et al., 2012). With increased global competitiveness and to tackle global manufacturing-related challenges, these digital systems are being promoted in the world's major industrial countries as a technology foundation for the manufacturing of the future (Chong et al., 2018; Paritala et al., 2017). Hence the need to identify current advances in the manufacturing of the future, in this case the Industry 4.0 (I4.0) initiative, is reviewed.

Liao et al. (2017) identify the main gaps in the I4.0 domain that refer to the difference between works that contain laboratory experiments (95.1%) and industrial applications (4.9%) in relation to I4.0. Xu et al. (2018) examine the evolution of Industry 1.0 (I1.0) to I4.0 by focusing on developing technologies that enable I4.0 and its challenges, including: integrating information and interoperability; standardisation related with cyber-physical systems (CPS) and the Internet of Things (IoT); cybersecurity and privacy of information; scalability problems when more objects are connected to the manufacturing network.

Kohler and Weisz (2016) define I4.0 as an approach to control production processes when providing the real-time synchronisation of flows and enabling the manufacture of unit and personalised products. By adopting this definition, Moeuf et al. (2018) acknowledge that complete knowledge about the exact requirements for small- and medium-sized enterprises (SME) to transform to I4.0 is still inexistent. For these authors, monitoring production processes is the easiest way to manage what can be achieved with I4.0-related technologies and resources. Likewise, Yin et al. (2018) revise the transformation of industries from I1.0 to I4.0 by comparing

them in accordance with technologies, the markets they target and production systems. These authors conclude that changes and requirements in production management principles and in customer demand in the I4.0 era remain unclear.

This article looks at the state of the art to mainly identify engineering requirements and production management in an I4.0 setting. To do so, it looks at technologies, the current situation of research into I4.0 as to what has been done to date, who works in it and the maturity of I4.0 today. The main contributions of this state of the art are to: (i) critically analyse the current state of research about incorporating the term I4.0 into engineering and production management; (ii) propose a classification of the main contributions made in revised articles in terms of design principles, technologies to enable I4.0 and reference conceptual frameworks; (iii) identify existing models and algorithms for production planning in the I4.0 context; (iv) identify and propose future research lines.

The rest of the article is arranged as follows: Section 2 presents the methodology followed to revise the literature; Section 3 offers the state of the art according to the proposed classification; Section 4 critically discusses the main aspects covered throughout the present state of the art; finally, the conclusion and future lines of work are provided.

2 Methodology

The methodology proposed for this literature review started by searching for the key words *industrie 4.0* and *industry 4.0*, and the considered documents and articles published until 2021. With this information, more documents and published articles were found to include the term *Industry 4.0*. Consequently after the initial review, the following key words were defined, which were always combined with the term *Industry 4.0*: *3D printing, additive manufacturing, augmented reality (AR), big data, blockchain, cloud computing, cloud manufacturing, communication, configuration, CPS, decision, digital twin, human, human-machine, Industrial Internet of Things, industrial network, integration, intelligence, intelligent, Internet of Things, manufacturing, operator, real time, smart, smart factory, transparency, virtual reality*. The main search criteria included filtering by the document or article title and by publication date for all the publications, including journals and proceeding of conferences, from 2011, which coincides with the time when the term I4.0 appeared in the scientific literature, to 2021. The literature search was done in different databases: Science Direct, IEEE Explore, Scopus, Google Scholar and Web of Science (WoS). Figure 1 illustrates the proposed methodology structure for the literature review.

Figure 1. Structure of the methodology followed for the literature review.

Next, scientific articles were selected, mainly, according to the proposed classification (Section 3). This led to the selection of 130 references from 1,733 identified articles that were considered representative to carry out this state of the art by considering, among other aspects, that they were scientific articles from journals and proceedings of the conferences indexed in the Scopus and WoS databases, their novelty and the number of citations received for these works in the Scopus and WoS databases.

3 Literature review

The term I4.0 emerged in 2011 to reinforce industrial production under the German term Industrie 4.0 (Kagermann et al. 2011). Hermann et al. (2016) propose nine clusters that represent the design principles of I4.0, including technical assistance, decentralised decision making, interconnection and information transparency. These authors conclude that the proposed design principles of I4.0 allow a better understanding of the term, as well as a better identification, description and definition of the different I4.0 scenarios. Table 1 lists the articles identified in the scientific literature that cover I4.0 principles (Hermann et al. (2016); Cañas and Mula, 2020). In addition, the fact that different previous literature reviews exist and have been contemplated throughout this article is highlighted (Table 2). Thus factories are one of the main components of

I4.0 where sensors, machines, conveyor belts and robots are connected to automatically exchange information and to obtain sufficient intelligence to predict and maintain machines. According to the I4.0 concept, smart factories are integrated in three ways: vertically, horizontally and end-to-end (Lucke et al. 2008). According to this smart factory concept, questions arise as to the role that humans will play in workplaces, and workers' mentality and competences, to provide help to different technologies.

Table 1. Comparison of I4.0 principles according to previous works.

Principle(s)	Hermann et al. (2016)	Qin et al. (2016)	Cohen et al. (2017)
Technical assistance	X		
Decentralised decisions	X		
Interconnection/connectivity	X		X
Information transparency	X		X
Intelligence/awareness		X	X
Knowledge			X
Interoperability		X	

Table 2. Previous I4.0 literature reviews contemplated throughout this paper.

Author(s)	Approach
Hozdić (2015)	Literature review of smart factories and their technological enablers, like the IoT, RFID (radio frequency identification) technology and CPS
Adeyeri et al. (2015)	Literature review of agents and multiagent from 2003 to 2014
Hermann et al. (2016)	I4.0 design principles
Cheng et al. (2016)	Review the development and application of I4.0 intelligent manufacturing (IM)
Waschneck et al. (2016)	Literature review of the different control methods that exist for complex job shops in the I4.0 context
Liao et al. (2017)	Present state of I4.0
Li et al. (2017)	Literature review of wireless networks (WNS) in the I4.0 context
Zhong et al. (2017)	Literature review of IM systems in an I4.0 environment
Davis (2017)	Literature review of the origin, present state and future advances of manufacturing
Wollschlaeger et al. (2017)	Review the technological tendencies and impact that industrial communication will have
Trappey et al. (2017)	Literature review of the standards and patents for the IoT. These authors build a standard I4.0 structure
Zhang et al. (2017a)	Literature review in which the scheduling and planning problem is dealt with in flow shops in the I4.0 context. These authors propose a reference framework
Zhang et al. (2017b)	Literature review of self-organising manufacturing systems (SOMS)
Xu et al. (2018)	Evolution of I4.0
Moeuf et al. (2018)	Production planning of SME in I4.0

Yin et al. (2018)	Evolution of production systems from I1.0 to I4.0
Ivanov et al. (2018)	Literature review of optimum control applications in production
Bordeleau et al. (2018)	Literature review of intelligence in businesses
Fernández-Carames and Fraga-Lamas (2018)	Literature review of the human-centred smart labels connected by the IoT needed for I4.0
Radanliev et al. (2018)	Cybersecurity risks for developing design principles for the IoT of I4.0
Ibarra et al. (2018)	Business processes that will be affected by I4.0
Fraga-Lamas et al. (2018)	Literature review of IAR (industrial AR) applications for I4.0 by proposing an architecture for IAR applications in a shipyard that they call Shipyard 4.0
Kritzinger et al. (2018)	Literature review of digital twin (DT) in manufacturing
Mehrpouya et al. (2019)	Review additive manufacturing
Alladi et al. (2019)	Review blockchain technology applications in the I4.0 and IIoT (Industrial Internet of Things) contexts
Usuga et al. (2019)	Review the literature about machine learning applied to production planning and control (PPC) activities and I4.0
Bueno et al. (2020)	Review PPC models in the I4.0 context
Parente et al. (2020)	Literature review of scheduling in I4.0 implementation
Da Silva and Guerreiro (2020)	Review 5G and beyond information and communication technologies (ICT) in the I4.0 context
Osterreider et al. (2020)	Literature review of the smart factory in the I4.0 context
Sepasgozar et al. (2020)	Identified challenges for 3DP (3D printing) implementation
Leng et al. (2020b)	Literature review of the blockchain technology adoption in SM and sustainability in an I4.0 context
Leng et al. (2021a)	Literature review of cybersecurity risks and blockchain technology in manufacturing systems
Scanzio et al. (2021)	Classification of heterogeneous industrial networks for I4.0
Neumann et al. (2021)	Review the human factor in I4.0 context implementations

From the works in Table 1 and Table 2, I4.0 principles were identified, and the articles about implementing I4.0 principles were collected and are classified in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Data collection results.

It is noteworthy that the principles of decentralised decision makings, intelligence/awareness, technology and business within the I4.0 framework have been mostly dealt with to date.

Table 4 shows the proposed I4.0 classification. It lists the reviewed articles according to categories without repeating them, along with the I4.0 principles previously identified, and the production planning category within which the present article is framed. It also includes the reference conceptual frameworks, which is one of the specific objectives to be identified with this state of the art.

Table 4. The I4.0 classification.

I4.0 principles, conceptual frameworks and production planning studies	Key words	Number of reviewed publications
Principles		
Interconnection/Connectivity	big data	4
	industrial network	7
Decentralised decision making	decision	4
Human factor	human	12
	operator	1
Intelligence/awareness	autonomous/self-configuration	4
	intelligence	2
	intelligent	4
	smart	20
Interoperability	communication	4
	CPS	5
	integration	8
	real time	1
Information transparency	transparency	0
Technology	3D	3
	AR	5
	VR	1
	cloud computing	4
	cloud manufacturing	1
	IoT/IIoT	4
	blockchain	7
	digital twin	7
Organisation	business	6
Conceptual frameworks	framework	8
Production planning studies	production planning	8
Total number of publications		130

The key words *big data*, *business*, *decision*, *human*, *smart*, *integration*, *intelligent*, and *IoT*, which were always linked with *industry 4.0*, appeared more times among the obtained results. The following main sources of the selected publications stand out: *Procedia Manufacturing*, *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, *IEEE Access* and *Procedia CIRP*, along with congress minutes. The following scientific journals stand out *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, *International Journal of Production Research*, *International Journal of Production Economics*, *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* and *Journal of Manufacturing Systems* (Table 5).

Table 5. The main sources of the selected I4.0 publications.

Source	Number
Proceedings of conferences	39
Procedia Manufacturing	11
IFAC-PapersOnLine	9
IEEE Access	7

Source	Number
Procedia CIRP	6
International Journal of Production Research	4
Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing	4
International Journal of Production Economics	4
Computer and Industrial Engineering	3
Computers in Industry	3
Advances in Engineering Informatics	2
Advanced Engineering Informatics	2
Computers Networks	2
IEEE Industrial Electronics Magazine	2
IEEE Sensors Journal	2
Journal of Manufacturing Systems	2
Processes	2
International Journal of Modern Manufacturing Technologies	2
Applied Sciences	1
Buildings	1
Cluster Computing	1
Encyclopedia of Sustainable Technologies	1
Energy and Buildings	1
Engineering	1
Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence	1
Frontiers of Mechanical Engineering	1
IEEE Communications Magazine	1
IEEE Emerging Technology and Factory Automation	1
IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology	1
International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks	1
Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing	1
Journal of Business Economics	1
Journal of Network and Computer Applications	1
Journal of Software Engineering and Applications	1
Journal of the International Measurement Confederation	1
Management and Production Engineering Review	1
Production Engineering	1
Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing	1
Sensors	1
Societies	1
Software and Systems Modeling	1
Wireless Networks	1
Total	130

Interconnection or connectivity refers to the enabling communication technologies between different electronic devices. Lee et al. (2014) propose a reference framework of a CPS with self-awareness and self-maintenance of machines by integrating the data acquired with sensors and

information about the fleet with which to reduce data volumes, and they must possess certain characteristics. Gölzer et al. (2015) present an analysis of the requirements related to I4.0 data processing, which are grouped into five main categories: *data model*, *data integration*, *data content*, *decision processing* and *knowledge processing*. Wang et al. (2016b) propose a “*self-decision making*” mechanism and the smart negotiation of mechanisms to implement a SOMS. The system’s architecture is based on a reference smart factory framework consisting in four tangible layers (Wang et al. 2016a): physical resources, the industrial network, the cloud and the supervisory control terminal. Lin et al. (2016) propose a metaheuristic algorithm for harmony searches, geometric selective harmony searches and a genetic algorithm with which they include a series of sensors and idle times in group-based industrial wireless sensors networks. In this context, the question arises about the type of connection that would be needed to process large volumes of information generated by production systems. Saldivar et al. (2015) believe that a new generation of wireless connections, such as 5G technology, will help to accelerate the rapid connectivity that I4.0 requires, and that mathematical models are necessary to integrate modelling languages into CPS environments. Li et al. (2017) propose a general I4.0 reference framework made up of four layers: a physical layer, a network, cloud or big data and an application layer. These authors illustrate a reference framework of industrial wireless networks (IWNs) divided into four components: smart entities, inter-IWNs, beyond IWNs, displays and servers. Wan et al. (2016) present a design prototype of a smart factory based on IWNs, a data cloud, smart machines and system management. In the I4.0 big data context, Reis and Gins (2017) analyse the evolution of industrial processes monitoring (IPM) from detection, diagnosis and what they believe will be the new interest in IPM: prognosis, which is based on the predictive capacities and tools of systems. Wollschlaeger et al. (2017) conclude that 5G technology will cover demands in real time and will replace today’s industrial automation networks. Da Silva and Guerreiro (2020) present a review of 5G ICT and a short overview of the future generation of telecommunications, 6G technology. For these authors, 5G will play an important role in the initial implementation of I4.0 where increased automation in industry will involve faster communication speed. Scanzio et al. (2021) propose a heterogeneous industrial networks classification, which consists of five categories: wired and WNs, technologies, technological aspects and performance targets. These authors address each category in which they identify wired and WNs technologies and techniques, and the main challenges, advantages, characteristics and communication requirements for industry applications. Among the many identified wired and wireless technologies, they conclude that software defined networking (SDN) and time-sensitive networking (TSN) form a potential standard backbone for the factories of the future.

Decentralised decision making must be automated and made in real time so that different artificial agents can be installed in production, planning and to deal with management processes. Terziyan et al. (2018) work on cloning human decision models for I4.0 with the help of the proposed Pi-Mind technology, which covers these requirements: interoperability, virtualisation, decentralisation, capacity of responding in real time and modularity. Simon et al. (2018) develop a mass customisation model in the food industry. They propose a multicriteria decision-making model based on a fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (FAHP) to minimise maintenance costs. They conclude that it is possible to adapt the I4.0 content elements of cloud computing, industrial big data, industrial networking, industrial robotics, 3D prototyping, knowledge-based automation, industrial communication security, VR and artificial intelligence in a mass customisation environment. Klement et al. (2017) propose a hybrid between a metaheuristic (simulated annealing) and a list algorithm for making decisions about the problems of planning, programming, assigning resources in production and lot scheduling in the hospital sector. As a second problem to solve, they consider scheduling lot sizing with due dates in the plastic injection sector. As a third application, they contemplate the precedence scheduling restrictions of different activities on an assembly line of metal components. They finally conclude that the model can be used to reconfigure a production system. Parente et al. (2020) identify research gaps and critical scheduling areas that may be impacted by I4.0 implementation. Indeed, agents should be capable of collecting available data to approach globally optimal decisions and schedules in decentralised environments. At the same time, they highlight the importance of tackling challenges related to complexity and computational requirements. They identify multiagent systems to model decentralised scheduling environments, metaheuristics, machine learning and hyperheuristics with a view to tackle I4.0 implementation challenges.

Regarding the human factor, Nelles et al. (2016) define that the human role in I4.0 is decision making to control and plan production. Hence the human factor role is to fulfil the requirements needed to implement technological and organisational methods (Gorecky et al., 2014). According to Hecklau et al. (2016), the competences that workers need can be classified as technical, methodological, social and personal. For Shamim et al. (2016), people's capacities are reflected in business management practices, which must contemplate learning, knowledge of management, compatibility with I4.0, smart factories, business processes, innovations and administrative approaches. Richert and Schuster (2016) deal with how to educate engineers for I4.0. They determine that it is necessary to reinforce the education competence and qualifications to face I4.0 challenges, and that it is also necessary to extend information technology skills for the next engineering generations. Therefore, virtual learning education (VLE) experiments and

studies are I4.0-oriented. Longo et al. (2017) investigate how to increase the capacities and competences of smart operators. To do so, they design and develop a reference methodological framework that they call SOPHOS-MS (a smart manufacturing (SM) system) that allows AR to be included in human-machine interactions. These authors combine the 5C architecture (smart connection level, data-to-information conversion level, cyber level, cognition level, configuration level) of Lee et al. (2015) and new approaches to support operators in manufacturing systems. For these authors, the human factor is the centre of gravity of SM systems as they benefit from operators' experience by creating feedback loops that allow the manufacturing system to grow and evolve. As for the human-machines interaction that needs to exist, Wittenberg (2016) analyse the effects of I4.0 in relation to mobile applications that support service and human maintenance technicians under the CPS influence of I4.0. Benešová and Tupa (2017) consider that employees' skills will be even more plentiful and must be classified according to a series of requirements due to the use of technology and smart production. They also believe that VLE will be the first step to educate employees, while the second step will involve AR. Fantini et al. (2018) propose a methodology to face the challenge of integrating workers with CPS systems and they put forward a reference framework made up of six components: abstraction, decision making, innovation, the human component, social interaction and the CPS component. They conclude that very little knowledge is available with which to design and adapt production systems when technological and human aspects are jointly considered to increase efficiency. Ansari et al. (2018) focus on the paradigm of changes made to work between humans and machines towards I4.0 production systems. To this end, they study human-machine mutual learning complications in future factories. Huber and Weiss (2017) present a study based on user experience (UX) by comparing two robotic arms in a human-robot interaction context in a production environment. Pfeiffer (2016) studies the assembly tasks of five firms in the automobile sector. This author determines that this sector is ideal to respond to the relations linking assembly work, the new technology options in robotics and future effects in contracting employees, and concludes that less qualified jobs are more susceptible to be replaced with robots. Kong et al. (2018) propose a manufacturing system that uses industrial wearable technology to establish an interface between humans and machines. These authors present a reference framework in an industrial wearable system (IWS) that enables all a manufacturing system's elements to collaborate. They identify gaps by investigating representative industrial wearable technology projects and the main components of an IWS that must be integrated with other technical components and form a support system for decision making as a whole. Neumann et al. (2021) review the literature in order to identify which aspects of human factors have been considered in the literature on I4.0 and to provide a framework to

systematically assess the impacts caused by I4.0 technology implementation on human workers and system performance. They conclude that current research into I4.0 technologies and implementation have mostly abandoned the human factor in I4.0 settings. It is worth stressing the difference between decentralised decision making and the human factor. The former is related to automated and real-time decision making, while the latter is related to the human factor aspects to be considered in I4.0 implementation, where there is a research gap in this direction.

As for intelligence or awareness and autonomous, for Vogel-Heuser et al. (2016) one characteristic that cyber-physical production systems (CPPS) must have is tolerance to defects and, consequently, of self-configuration and restart, which allow overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) to increase. With awareness or self-awareness in I4.0, it is achieved when a machine is capable of recognising itself as part of a whole and is given knowledge about what the team's goal is, as well as recognising its role to fulfil that goal (Parente et al. 2020).

Regarding configuration, Legat and Vogel-Heuser (2017) propose the configurable planning of partial production orders based on a combination of goals-based formulated planning and reformulate it by linear programming. They developed an automated planning model, HiTraP-AT (hierarchical transition planner for automation technology) in an I4.0 environment. Müller et al. (2017) focus on the automated flow lines design problem by considering redundancies in operations based on I4.0 technologies. Zhang et al. (2017b) revise SOMS and analyse their different approaches, concepts and mechanisms. They establish that ICT are enablers to run an SOMS among them: IoT, CPS, cloud manufacturing, big data, proactive computing, predictive and automated decision making, 3DP, mobile robots and autonomous navigation vehicles. Klement, Silva and Gibaru (2017) developed a tool based on a metaheuristics and heuristics hybrid to support strategic decision making that is to be employed as part of I4.0 to design reconfigurable production systems.

Yao et al. (2017) compare IM and SM systems, their evolution and the status of today's IM/SM. They consider that SM consists in incorporating artificial intelligence. They identify that the CPS architecture does not suffice for either I4.0 or a manufacturing system, but they believe it is necessary to include a social dimension. To do so, they propose a reference SM framework which they call SCPS (social cyberphysical system). Bordeleau et al. (2018) present a bibliometric review of firms' intelligence in an I4.0 environment and determine the gaps and opportunities in the intelligence of businesses.

Albers et al. (2016) focus on intelligent quality control systems in a procedure that defines a system's objectives in an initial I4.0 phase. They state that no systematic approach exists to enable I4.0 in SME. Cheng et al. (2016) review the development and application of IM for I4.0.

They take digitisation as a part of intelligence, and IM to be the basis of digital manufacturing. The latter is the end result of IM as a basis for I4.0. Zhong et al. (2017) construct a reference IM framework and analyse IM systems in an I4.0 environment by comparing key concepts like SM, cloud manufacturing and IoT-enabled manufacturing. Yan et al. (2017) propose a strategy to respond to the big data generated with manufacturing systems which they base on intelligent prognostics.

It is worth stressing the difference between the terms smart and intelligence. A smart factory is understood as one that exploits its intelligence capacities as much as possible. Wang et al. (2021) systematically review the literature on differences in an SM and an IM system. The authors identify the terminology, architectures, key capabilities, principles, relations and common enabling technologies in both paradigms.

Hozdić (2015) reviews the smart factory and its technological enablers, such as the IoT, RFID and CPS. According to a literature review, they consider that a smart factory must have these characteristics: be flexible, reconfigurable, low-cost, capable of changing, agile and lean. Here it is important to distinguish between smart and smart connected in the I4.0 literature. The latter refers to the connection of physical manufacturing equipment and devices over the internet together with big data analytics in the digital world (Zhong et al. 2017; Aheleroff et al. 2020).

Paelke (2014) presents an AR system in a smart factory environment, and identifies that by using AR in productivity, spatial planning and navigation system applications are beginning to become commonplace. Shrouf et al. (2014) present a reference architecture for smart factories based on the IoT with an approach they follow to see how this improves energy efficiency. Schmidt et al. (2015) conduct a quantitative study about the potential of I4.0, big data and cloud computing technologies. Their results confirm that today's big data, cloud computing, mobile computing, IoT and CPS technologies positively affect the use of I4.0 because they are the basis and driver of I4.0. Zawadzki and Zywicki (2016) propose a general smart design concept and production control as the key elements for SM. They present mass product customisation challenges. Ang et al. (2016) determine that one key enabler for I4.0 smart design in a mass customisation and low-cost context is computational intelligence based on computer automated design (CAutoD). Waschneck et al. (2016) present a literature review of the different control methods available for complex job shops in the I4.0 context. They identify how a few ideas are exchanged between job shop programming and I4.0. Zhang et al. (2017a) deal with the flow shop programming problem in the I4.0 context by devising different taxonomies of optimisation algorithms to programme and characterise them. They build a reference framework to solve the flow shop problem under I4.0 and its enabling technologies. Batista et al. (2017) propose an architecture based on information

technologies for I4.0, which they call the industry 4.0 service enabler architecture (I4SEA). This architecture enables the added value services of smart grids and smart living to be created according to I4.0 design principles. Chen et al. (2017) propose a hierarchical I4.0 SM architecture and analyse the key technologies for layers of physical resources, the network layer and the data application layer. They state that no standard is available to implement a smart factory. For these authors, all the physical resources involved in a product's life cycle are the basis for SM. Kusiak, A. (2017) studies the origin, current state and future advances in manufacturing by defining the key concepts in a SM system, but without identifying a generally accepted definition of SM. This author concludes that SM is based not only on the automation level, but the autonomy, evolution, simulation and optimisation of companies' manufacturing must also be contemplated. Zheng et al. (2018) put forward a conceptual framework of I4.0 SM systems that is formed by a horizontal axis represented by smart design, smart control, smart programming and smart machining. The use of sensors and actuators, data analysis and decision making comprises the vertical axis. Guo et al. (2017) propose the design and architecture of a passive optical access network (PON) to connect machines to a control centre that would be capable of making known the status of machines in real time; that is, for a smart factory. Küsters et al. (2017) present the 4.0 textile learning factory of the Institut für Textiltechnik der RWTH Aachen University in Aachen, Germany. Li et al. (2017) propose two algorithms based on smart negotiation to face multiagent system complexities. Fernandez-Carames and Fraga-Lamas (2018) offer a literature review of human-centred smart labels connected by the IoT required for I4.0. They consider that implementing I4.0 needs the integration principles of technologies like the IoT, CPS, vertical and horizontal integration systems, additive manufacturing 3DP, big data and data analytics, cybersecurity, cloud and edge computing, simulation software, robots and automatic vehicles, and both virtual and ARs. Gershwin (2018) studies the inclusion of human intuition in manufacturing systems and the role played by humans in both the design and operations of manufacturing systems.

Latorre-Biel et al. (2018) formulate a petri net model for the virtualisation of a smart factory's decision making in an I4.0 environment. Osterreider et al. (2020) present a literature review of the smart factory concept by categorising it into eight research fields: decision making, CPS, data handling, ICT infrastructure, digital transformation, human machine interaction, IoT and cloud manufacturing.

Table 6 identifies the technological enablers of a smart factory, and its characteristics, key elements, reference architectures, algorithms for decision making and states of the art.

Table 6. Smart manufacturing

Technological enablers	Cloud computing, edge computing, big data, data analytics, IoT, 3DP, cybersecurity, AR, VR, mobile computing, IWNs, CAutoD, robots, autonomous vehicles, drones, CPS, sensors and actuators
Characteristics	Reconfigurable manufacturing, autonomy, flexibility, visibility, agile, lean, mass customisation, productivity, quality, speed, standardisation, additive manufacturing, connected supply chain
Key elements	Smart design, production control, digitalisation, automation, cybersecurity, security, connectivity, interoperability, monitoring, virtualisation, coordination, collaboration, real time, sustainability
Reference architectures	I4SEA, hierarchical I4.0 architecture, IoT-based architecture
Algorithms for decision making	Modelling, optimisation, simulation

Companies face many challenges due to lack of interoperability. They need to more quickly adapt to changes in the business and economic market and to more swiftly respond to customer requirements. Although companies strongly depend on ICT-based solutions for their day-to-day business operations, these solutions are not often flexible and are hard to adapt to fulfil these changing companies' requirements (Truex et al. 1999; Boza et al. 2009; Hernández et al. 2010; Vargas et al. 2011). Interoperability is a vital problem when it comes to sharing information and interchanging services. It goes beyond simple technical computer hardware and software problems because it deals with what are still widely and precisely identified barriers not only in relation to data and services, but also respect processes and businesses (INTEROP- DI.1b, 2006). Definitions of interoperability have been profoundly reviewed (Chen and Vernadat, 2002; Chen and Lee, 2004; Weichhart et al. 2017). From the computing technology viewpoint, it is the faculty of two heterogeneous computing systems that jointly provides reciprocal access to their resources. In the companies' network context, it refers to the capacity to interact (exchange data and services) among business systems.

Communication is considered a means by which to achieve interoperability between machines and humans. Wollschlaeger et al. (2017) reviewed technological trends and the impact that industrial communication, the IoT and CPS would have on industrial automation in the I4.0 context. They identify that mass interest is shown by telecommunication industries in industrial applications as the result of adopting the IoT and CPS. 5G technology is expected to be able to cover real-time automation demands and to replace the industrial networks used for automation. Schlechtendahl et al. (2014) believe that the I4.0 factory will enable the possibility of detecting and being connected to a CPS. Therefore, they recommend an industrial communication protocol: OPC UA (open platform communications unified architecture). Lucas-Estañ et al. (2018) propose

software for hierarchical communication and an architecture to manage data for I4.0. They determine that two I4.0 technological enablers are a communication infrastructure that would support the ubiquitous connectivity of cyberphysical production systems (CPPS) and data management outlines.

CPS are characterised by three phases: the first generation includes identifications with RFID labels; the second generation is equipped with actuator sensors with a limited range of functions; the third-generation CPS can store and analyse data, and are equipped with multiple sensors and actuators that are compatible with networks (Bauernhansl et al. 2014). Bagheri et al. (2015) propose an architecture to integrate CPS into manufacturing using the 5C architecture of Lee et al. (2015). This architecture is based on design methodologies and guides, and on launching CPS for manufacturing from data acquisition to data analysis and creating value. Mosterman and Zander (2016) present some specific examples of the challenges of CPS as collaboration systems that must perform a given task, including collaborative planning, guide and control, multirate architectures, drawing and deriving specific values from general information, the multiuse post-development functionality, the interaction characteristic, generating automatic tests, automated evaluation tests and reproducing test results with a minimum of uncertainty. Guizzi et al. (2017) propose a semi-hierarchical architecture for I4.0 production planning that is a reference framework with no practical algorithmic solution. The architecture they contemplate is a first attempt to face NP-hard problem in job shop scheduling. Jiang (2017) proposes an architecture to integrate CPS into manufacturing and calls it 8C (connection, conversion, cyber, cognition, configuration, coalition, customer and content). This author takes the 5C architecture of Lee et al. (2015) as a basis to add 3C more, namely coalition, customer and content.

The intention of integration is to connect different business processes of a company so that they can be communicated and distinct tasks can be performed in the same system. Tvenge et al. (2018) describe how learning activities can be integrated into cyber-physical manufacturing systems in an I4.0 environment. Schlechtendahl et al. (2015) present a holistic approach to make production systems transformable to I4.0 by integrating CPPS. For these authors, the gateway is a key enabler for production systems to form part of I4.0, which they indicate that they are not presently prepared for a CPPS. Adeyeri et al. (2015) review the literature about agents and multiagent systems from 2003 to 2014. They propose a reference framework for a reconfigurable manufacturing system that contains agents of: maintenance, vision, control, order, software, machine, artificial intelligence, resources and the system. According to Saldivar et al. (2015), I4.0 includes cyber-virtual systems and CPS to support SM, and to connect data and physical resources. Fernández-Miranda et al. (2017) examine the challenges of integrating I4.0 into

mechanical engineering. Such challenges include training in which 4.0 requires a very high demand of specialists to build and maintain these factories, standardisation to exchange data among machines, systems and software in the value chain, secure data, etc. Molano et al. (2017) propose a metamodel to integrate the IoT, social networks and I4.0 cloud computing. They conclude that one obstacle to prevent the IIoT from being implemented is interoperability of systems because they belong to different suppliers. So these authors indicate that interfaces must be standardised to accomplish interoperability. Cicconi et al. (2017) put forward a model and simulation of the heat induction process for an aluminium-steel mould used to produce soles of shoes. With their qualitative literature study, Radanliev et al. (2018) propose an integration that allows a reference framework to be standardised for cybersecurity. According to Boyes et al. (2018), what difference lies in a CPS and ICT system is real-time communication with the physical world, and the main focus is achieving control over physical processes in CPS. Fuchs et al. (2017) propose tests to monitor the real time of latency, path delay and synchronisation quality of Ethernet in industrial applications.

Two major I4.0 reference architectures have been standardised, namely: Reference Architecture Model Industry 4.0 (RAMI 4.0) by the German Electrical and Electronic Manufacturing (ZVEI, 2015); Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA) by the Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC, 2017). RAMI 4.0 consists of a three-dimensional model in which the vertical axis represents the layers used to represent data map perspectives, functional descriptions, communication behaviours, hardware/assets or business processes based on the international standard for enterprise integration and control IEC 62890 (Adolphs et al., 2015). The horizontal axis represents the hierarchical levels based on IEC 62264/61512, the enterprise level, work centres, stations and control devices. IIRA provides five description layers of the tasks of an industrial system, their interrelation, structure and interactions; the layers are businesses, application, information, operations and control (Needham, 2015). Both architectures are based on the hierarchical model of ANSI/ISA-95, i.e., the automation pyramid of 5C (Moghaddam et al. 2018). Yli-Ojanperä et al. (2019) determine that OPC UA is a key standard technology for the RAMI 4.0 architecture and for the DDS (data distribution service) of IIRA, and both for supplying data availability in real time to all users in a connected world. Another standard is the I4.0 component model, which defines an administration layer for each component and enables interoperability of technology among different vendors (Zezulka et al. 2016).

Regarding technology, in the I4.0 context, the additive manufacturing concept has been used interchangeably with 3DP technology. Additive manufacturing has been defined by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) and the International Organisation for Standardisation

(ISO) as the process of joining materials to make parts from a three-dimensional model data, usually layer upon layer, as opposed to subtractive manufacturing and formative manufacturing technologies. With 3DP, it refers to the manufacturing of objects via the deposition of a material using a print head, nozzle, or another printer technology.

Montes (2016) analyses the effect of 3DP on business models with 25 case studies. For the analysis, this author classifies five types of companies that work with 3DP: manufacturers of end products, manufacturers of 3D printers, companies that use 3DP to create prototypes, developers and distributors of 3D printers. It creates a conceptual 3DP framework and business models. Its obtained results indicate that 3DP influences the value of communication, distribution and data collection. While Mehrpouya et al. (2019) review the literature on additive manufacturing and I4.0 in terms of technologies, materials and challenges. Sepasgozar et al. (2020) review additive manufacturing applications for I4.0 and identify the main 3DP implementation challenges, such as on-site technology and the used material.

For Masoni et al. (2017), AR is a leading technology for I4.0. One of the reasons why it has not been introduced into industrial practice is its poor software/hardware performance-cost ratio. These authors present several technology problems, such as exactness in tracking algorithms, speed of internet connections, lighting conditions and information to be projected in AR that enables effective maintenance tasks. Mourtzis et al. (2018) develop an application that incorporates AR to train product design engineers. Fraga-Lamas et al. (2018) review basic characteristics and analyse IAR systems for industrial applications, specifically for shipbuilders. These authors propose an architecture for IAR applications for a shipbuilder, which they call Shipyard 4.0. In this context, Blanco-Novoa et al. (2018) apply different IAR hardware and software tools that form part of the Shipyard 4.0 project.

Kovar et al. (2016) deal with VR in the I4.0 context and identify two groups: monocular semi-immersive VR and totally immersive VR, which contemplates binocular headsets and CAVE VR. They conclude that AR has marked capabilities in industry by enabling workers to be smoothly integrated into the digital environment. However, AR technology has not yet matured. These authors address the importance of how to adapt processes for AR technology and how to align them in current systems, while ensuring workers' health and safety.

Cloud computing can be defined as an access network demanded for some shared common pool of configurable computing resources (networks, servers, storage, applications and services, among others) that can be quickly provisioned and released with minimum management effort or by interacting with the service provider (Mell and Grance, 2011). Additionally, the terms distributed and decentralised refer to the extension of cloud computing to the fog computing

architecture, which supports the physically distributed, low latency and quality of services aware applications to reduce network traffic and distributed and autonomous decision making, and to improve scalability and enhance security for CPS in I4.0 (Donovan et al. 2019; Fernández-Caramés et al. 2019).

Yen et al. (2014) consider that a cloud platform is a basic component of the reference framework of a CPS. Moreover, an embedded system and a sensor network form part of this framework. They distinguish the core values of a cloud platform as being storage, cloud computing and sharing. For these authors, cloud computing leads to new information technologies by supplying resources as centralised sharing and flexible expansion, as well as new business models and opportunities for cloud services. Thames and Schaefer (2016) propose a software-defined cloud manufacturing (SDCM) architecture where the intention is to accomplish characteristics of I4.0 systems. They indicate that a software-defined system has the characteristics of being agile, programmable, manageable, configurable, interoperable, adaptable and protectable. For these authors, cloud-based manufacturing (CBM) will significantly contribute to I4.0 by possessing the characteristics of being a network manufacturing model, infrastructure-as-a-service, platform-as-a-service, hardware-as-a-service and software-as-a-service, etc. In this context, it is worth stressing cloud platform C2NET (Lauras et al. 2015; Andres et al. 2016b), which helps to supply chain companies to collaborate in optimising production plans, replenishment and distribution. The C2NET platform is made up of three main modules: the Data Collection Framework (DCF) for continuous data collection based on the IoT using supply network resources; the Network Optimiser (OPT) to optimise manufacturing assets and supply network logistics; Collaboration Tools (COT) to support the collaborative processes of the supply network. The main Network Optimiser (OPT) component is Optimisation Algorithms, which currently integrate 50 mathematical optimisation models, and heuristic, metaheuristic and matheuristic algorithms capable of solving a range of production, replenishment and distribution plans corresponding to the overall purpose (Andres et al. 2016a; Andres et al. 2017). He et al. (2017) propose an LLRU (locally-aware least recently used) algorithm through flash memory that allows cloud computing optimisation to exploit reuse and location probability characteristics. Ma et al. (2017) propose an architecture or I4.0 operating system for the virtualisation of a network of companies based on the IoT and cloud computing by using an integrated system infrastructure made up of four layers: a software-defined infrastructure, a virtualisation network, a control level and the virtualisation of network functions.

The IoT is a technology that enables industries to shift to an I4.0 environment by including intelligence in products and their processes throughout the supply chain. Wan et al. (2016)

propose a software-defined IIoT architecture to manage physical devices and to supply an interface to exchange information. Trappey et al. (2017) review IoT standards and patents. They divide IoT technologies into four layers: perception, transmission, computing and application. Ding et al. (2018) propose a reference framework for the smart building of steel bridges in the I4.0 context by applying information building modelling and IoT.

The first digital twin (DT) definition was given by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) as an integrated multi-physics, multi-scale, probabilistic simulation of a vehicle or system that uses the best available physical models, sensor updates, fleet history, etc., to mirror the life of its flying twin (Shafto et al. 2010). Kritzinger et al. (2018) identify that recent research focusing on the DT is to deal with PPC activities along with simulation modelling. The main differences of the DT to simulation are given by the data integration level, where the latter is only a technological enabler for its implementation. These authors categorise DTs according to the data integration level in a digital model, digital shadow and DT. Uhlemann et al. (2017) present a concept for the realisation of the DT in a SME. Wagner et al. (2017) difference between the terms DT and asset administration shell, where the second one refers to a virtual digital and active representation of an I4.0 component in an I4.0 system. Vachalék et al. (2017) present a DT concept and demonstrate the interaction of real production processes with a digital simulation model. Rosen et al. (2015) highlight the importance of the DT to the manufacturing of I4.0. Qi and Tao (2018) review and compare the concepts of the DT and big data in manufacturing where the DT is defined as an integrated way for physical and the cyber world, providing the manufacturing enterprises with a new way to carry out smart production and precision management. In this sense, Wang and Wang (2018) propose a DT-based system architecture for waste electrical and electronic equipment recovery. Liu et al. (2019) propose a DT of a rapid design of an automated flow-shop manufacturing system (AFMS) in the individualisation/customisation paradigm. The DT approach integrates discrete event models and system dynamics modelling to evaluate design decisions in the AFMS context. The DT provides a design with intelligent optimisation and simulation. Leng et al. (2019a) propose a DT architecture to integrate real-time data into a warehouse product-service system and an optimisation algorithm to achieve a dynamic optimising warehouse system. Leng et al. (2019b) propose the architecture of the DT-driven manufacturing of a CPS (MCPS). MCPS builds a connection between smart workpieces and smart resources by forming a closed loop service system. MCPS focuses on the parallel control of a smart workshop in the mass individualisation/customisation context. The authors conclude that future research should focus on the integration of big data analytics into the proposed DT model to operate a manufacturing system. Leng et al. (2020a) propose a DT architecture to achieve a rapid

reconfigurable manufacturing system (RMS). The DT architecture consists of two levels, where the first level is a semiphysical simulation that maps all kinds of data to feed the optimisation level. The objective of optimisation is to find an optimal configuration. The authors propose a three-level platform of an RMS as techniques to be addressed by the DT-driven approach. The platform is divided into a system level, a control level and a machine level. Liu et al. (2021) propose a method to bridge the gap between design and operation in I4.0 cyber models that mirror physical systems. The authors propose a DT-based design of flow-type smart manufacturing systems. The DT is based on an architecture of configuration, motion, control and optimisation design model. Aheleroff et al. (2021) present a DT reference architecture model based on RAMI 4.0, and introduce the DT as a service (DTaaS) by utilising cloud, IoT and AR technologies to foster I4.0 transformation.

Blockchain is a technology that has, mainly, become popular in fields like finance and it is behind cryptocurrency bitcoin (Nakamoto, 2008). Blockchain is based on a database that creates a distributed and immutable digital ledger of transactions or agreements on a certain activity (Viriyasitavat et al. 2018). The agreed activities are registered and stored in data blocks, timestamped, encrypted and shared with other entities (Mohamed and Al-Jaroodi, 2019). Fernández-Caramés and Fraga-Lamas (2019) review the benefits and challenges involved when using blockchain and smart contracts to develop I4.0 applications. They conclude that blockchain can enhance I4.0 technologies by providing security, trust, immutability, decentralisation and higher automation through smart contracts. In this sense, Fernández-Caramés et al. (2019) define smart contracts as self-sufficient decentralised codes executed autonomously when certain conditions of a business are met. Lin et al. (2018) considers smart contracts to be fundamental to ensure scalability in I4.0 applications. They proposed a blockchain-based system framework for I4.0 deployments. Alladi et al. (2019) address blockchain technology applications in different industry sectors: healthcare, supply chain and logistics, power industry, agriculture, manufacturing, e-commerce and retail, education and UAV industry, among others. Lohmer et al. (2020) study supply chain resilience and blockchain technology in the risk management context. They believe that the inclusion of blockchain could lead to a comprehensive change in the design and operation of supply chains by increasing visibility and enabling real-time data sharing in their network, which would reduce the partners affected by disruptions and support supply chain resilience strategies. Leng et al. (2019c) combine blockchain and DT technology in a manufacturing system architecture, dubbed as ManuChain, in the IIoT and I4.0 context. ManuChain aims to eliminate the imbalance between manufacturing planning and execution caused by dynamic changes in complex manufacturing systems. It consists of a bi-level

intelligence platform based on permissioned blockchain-based networks and a holistic iterative optimisation DT. ManuChain contains I4.0 features, such as self-organising among devices/resources/smart gateways, customisation/individualisation and decentralisation. The authors conclude that their architecture can be improved by combining it with artificial intelligence algorithms and big data analytics. Along these lines, Leng et al. (2019d) propose the Makerchain architecture, which combines blockchain and smart contracts for a decentralised self-organising social manufacturing system. Leng et al. (2020b) review the literature related to blockchain technology adoption in the SM context of I4.0. In their study, blockchain is approached as a new IS generation in which its transparency and traceability are features of potential enablers to achieve sustainability in manufacturing systems and PLM. The authors propose a two-dimensional framework of a blockchain-based sustainable manufacturing system. The framework comprises two perspectives: the first refers to the manufacturing system in which blockchain can be used as a driver in the existing ERP (enterprise resources planning) and MES (manufacturing execution system). The second perspective refers to the PLM. The authors discuss that the data exchange and management are challenging given intellectual property protection, security and trust issue needs. Leng et al. (2021a) review the literature on cybersecurity risks in information management and blockchain technology as part of current manufacturing systems. Their review, which consists of 159 articles, mainly takes as a reference cybersecurity risks in manufacturing systems and blockchain applications in a PPC (i.e., scheduling, manufacturing management, resource planning). Furthermore, frameworks related to smart contracts, decentralised production systems and their challenges are reviewed. The authors identify eight cybersecurity risks in manufacturing systems: traceability, cyber-attacks, advanced viruses in control systems, device counterfeiting and false authentication in data sharing, interoperability, participants' confidentiality and trust, information vulnerability and reliability across systems, and failures at key nodes when centralised platforms are in place. To address cybersecurity risks, the authors propose a smart factory reference architecture insofar as blockchain enables decentralisation in a peer-to-peer communication system in which information can be arranged between machines by implementing computation to networked devices and to, thus, lower the costs of large data centres. The architecture consists of four blockchain-based computation layers, an ANSI/ISA-95 architecture and blockchain application components. The authors discuss how a blockchain-secured SM architecture covers data management aspects like data protection, availability, security, confidentiality, provenance, integrity, service, accountability, consistency, analysis, synchronisation, scale and mutability. They conclude that deploying such a blockchain-secured SM architecture entails its own challenges related to blockchain itself, such as developing

consensus algorithms, signature algorithms, data mutability and data protection mechanisms and privacy. According to Leng et al. (2021b), current research progress in relation to blockchain security has been addressed mostly from a technical perspective. Their surveyed blockchain security from an IS perspective divides it into a three-level security framework (i.e., process, data and infrastructure levels). The process security level refers to smart contracts, implementing scenarios, standards/regulations, fraud detection and risk management. Data security refers to access control in a blockchain system, computing techniques on encrypted blockchain data, retrieval techniques on encrypted data, signature schemes in blockchain, privacy protection techniques and consensus algorithms. The infrastructure security level refers to private key management from a user's perspective, terminal and networking vulnerability, and compliance enablement. Therefore, future research directions based on the framework's levels, such as big data analytics for blockchain process security, are proposed; anti-quantum computing signature methods for data security; middleware interfaces for multiblockchains for infrastructure security, among others.

On organisation, Petrasch and Hentschke (2016) present a modelling language called the I4.0 modelling language (I4PML) and define a method to model I4.0 applications (I4PMM). This language is an extension of the unified modelling language (UML) profile non-modified BPMN 2.0 (business process model and notation) stereotypes. These authors provide an example of modelling processes using I4PML in a conveyor belt system. Wang et al. (2016a) investigate implementing smart factories into an I4.0 environment by a vertical integration approach. Zezulka et al. (2016) introduce into the literature the reference architecture model for I4.0 called RAMI 4.0, and also the I4.0 component models developed by BITCOM, VDMA and ZWEI. Moghaddam et al. (2018) analyse the reference architectures for SM set out in the literature, including RAMI 4.0, IIRA, IBM I4.0 and NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) SM. RAMI and IIRA are described earlier in the present article. IBM 4.0 is a reference bi-layer architecture that describes the functional architecture of a manufacturing system (IBM, 2018), whose layers are: cloud platform/hybrid and devices/equipment. NIST adopts a services-oriented approach. Lu et al. (2016) provide an NIST functioning architecture of an industrial firm. Ibarra et al. (2018) examine how business processes will be affected by I4.0, analyse 26 articles and divide them into three main blocks: I4.0 characteristics, and challenges and requirements related to business processes.

Reference conceptual frameworks, business processes, reference models and maturity models need to be developed, understood and evaluated to implement I4.0 with a technology-based approach, human beings and processes (Oesterreich and Teuteberg, 2016). Qin et al. (2016) use

the 5C architecture proposed by Lee et al. (2015) to present a reference conceptual framework to classify I4.0 manufacturing systems. Their framework combines level of intelligence with level of engineering by generating nine intelligence applications; the lowest level corresponds to a low level of intelligence and simple automation, while the highest level indicates a high level of intelligence and complex automation. Wang et al. (2017) propose a reference conceptual framework for mass customised production based on I4.0 concepts made up of several layers: networks, the Internet of Services (IoS), a warehouse management system, CPS, enterprise information systems (EIS) and a system to run production. These authors believe that I4.0 has four key components: CPS; mobile and cloud computing (the IoT); big data, data mining and knowledge discovery; the IoS. Bücken et al. (2016) propose a I4.0 reference framework based on human, technological and organisational concepts to represent the organisational dimension. They also use the I4.0 design principles (interconnection, information transparency, decentralised decision making and technical assistance) of Herman et al. (2016). The authors conclude that the proposed framework can help researchers to acquire knowledge in the I4.0 context. This framework seeks efficiency through the human-technology interaction that allows high levels of autonomy to enable more efficient processes (Bauer et al. 2014). Lu (2017) puts forward a reference conceptual framework for I4.0 interoperability broken down into four levels: operational (organisational), systematic (applicable), technical and interoperable semantic. Cohen et al. (2017) present a reference conceptual framework to implement an assembly system based on the principles of connectivity, information, knowledge and I4.0 intelligence. This reference framework has been validated with a case study of a manufacturer of industrial refrigerators. Weking et al. (2020) develop a framework to describe, analyse and classify business models for I4.0. Table 7 compares the main reference conceptual frameworks related to I4.0.

Table 7. Reference conceptual framework related to I4.0.

Principle	Wang et al. (2016a) (517 TC)*	Lu (2017) (797 TC)*	Qin et al. (2016) (317 TC)*	Zheng et al. (2018) (165 TC)	Adeyeri et al. (2015) (27 TC)*	Cohen et al. (2017) (40 TC)*	Bücken et al. (2016) (15 TC)*
Interconnection/Connectivity	x		x	x	x	x	x
Information transparency							x
Decentralised decision making							x
Technical assistance							x
Human Factor						x	x
Technology	x		x	x	x	x	x
Organisation							x
Intelligence/Awareness	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Knowledge			x				

Interoperability	X	X	X	X	X
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TC= Total Citations *Consulted in Scopus on 26 January 2021

To classify I4.0 production planning models, we consider the proposal by Giannoccaro and Pontrandolfo (2001), who identify four kinds of modelling approaches or models: conceptual, analytical, simulation and artificial intelligence. Conceptual models consist in the descriptive tools that underline the main aspects and relevant variables involved in a given problem and/or empirical structures that propose guidelines to deal with problems. The analytical models herein considered are based on different operational research techniques, mainly linear programming, dynamic programming, integer mixed programming, multi-objective programming, Markov processes and analytical hierarchy process (AHP), and also on control theory, like optimum control models. Models based on artificial intelligence are, in turn, based on expert systems, fuzzy sets theory, fuzzy logic, neuronal networks, genetic algorithms, reinforcement learning and multiagent systems. Simulation models can contemplate mainly simulations based on system dynamics, discrete event simulation or Petri nets. We now go on to present a representative sample of these simulation analytical models and artificial intelligence models in an I4.0 environment, as we have already looked at conceptual models (see Table 7). Sokolov and Ivanov (2015) use an approach known as structure dynamics control (SDC) (Ivanov et al. 2009). It is based on the combined application of the optimum programme control (OPC) theory and mathematical programming for the design and dynamic programming of services in cyber-physical supply networks in the I4.0 context. These authors stress the importance for the short-term planning of I4.0 smart factories based on the collaboration of CPS as the way that industrial networks will be in the future. Ivanov et al. (2016a) propose a new structure dynamics control (SDC) model to coordinate services and physical flows in cyber-physical supply chains in the I4.0 context based on Sokolov and Ivanov (2015). For operational decisions, Ivanov et al. (2016b) put forward a new SDC model to programme a flexible flow shop with continuous flows and discrete assignments in an I4.0 environment. Schuh et al. (2014) propose a production network design with optimum migration paths that focus on I4.0 using genetic algorithms to identify the trade-off paths between the costs of migrating from one production network to another and the total costs related to future network scenarios. Ivanov, Dolgui and Sokolov (2017) develop an OPC and an algorithm to plan a flow shop based on a flexible industry 4.0 assembly line. To do so, they consider two principles: using the results obtained in decision programming modelling with OPC; using a computing procedure based on the Hamiltonian maximum and maximisation principles. Usuga et al. (2019) review the literature on machine learning applied to PPC activities in an SM of I4.0. They identify techniques and tools to implement a machine learning-PPC approach.

Readers are referred to Bueno et al. (2020) for a more extensive literature review on PPC models in the I4.0 context.

It is worth highlighting that more analytical models appear for I4.0 production planning, followed by artificial intelligence and simulation models, to deal with I4.0-related problems (Table 8).

Table 8. Summary of I4.0 analytical, artificial intelligence and simulation models

Authors	Model	Resolution algorithm	Modelling approach/Objectives
Sokolov and Ivanov (2015)	Analytical	x	SDC model for the design and dynamic programming of I4.0 cyber-physical supply network services
Ivanov et al. (2016a)	Analytical	x	SDC model to coordinate services and physical flows in I4.0 cyber-physical supply network
Ivanov et al. (2016b)	Analytical	x	Dynamic model and algorithm for programming flexible flow shops with continuous flows and discrete assignments in an I4.0 setting
Lin et al. (2016)	Artificial Intelligence	x	Harmony search metaheuristics, geometric selective harmony search and genetic algorithm for programming's that reduce energy use
Cicconi et al. (2017)	Simulation		CPS simulation model that considers the time and energy use of an LGV (laser-guided vehicle). A CPPS architecture is proposed
Ivanov et al. (2017)	Analytical	x	SDC model and resolution algorithm to plan a flow shop on a flexible assembly line
Klement et al. (2017)	Artificial Intelligence	x	Simulated annealing and a heuristic (list algorithm) for production planning
Latorre-Biel et al. (2018)	Simulation		Petri Net model for the virtualisation of a smart factory's decision making
Müller et al. (2017)	Analytical		Linear programming model to design automated flow lines by considering redundancy in operations
Simon et al. (2018)	Analytical		AHP model for mass customisation in the food industry
Terziyan et al. (2018)	Artificial Intelligence		Artificial intelligence model, Pi-mind, based on multiagent systems for decision making in the smart factory context

4 Discussion

After the review of 130 I4.0 studies, it is worth highlighting that the confusion between the term I4.0 and constant evolution at the same rate as technological advances has been corroborated. This represents a challenge for companies, specifically for SMEs, which could confuse I4.0 with unnecessary technological investment. Therefore, the following definition of I4.0 is proposed: "flexible production systems, with or without human interaction, that clone their knowledge and experience with algorithms, models, heuristics, metaheuristics, matheuristics and hyperheuristics to enable them to be self-configurable, self-maintaining, self-aware, self-designed, sustainable,

and both intelligent and smart to make decisions". Our insight into these new production systems lies in them being interconnected by a virtual cloud platform infrastructure connected to a cloud computing network that uses software (language and gateway) and a real hardware infrastructure. They exchange big data and reciprocal indications, or with humans, in real time by the Internet (wireless) or Ethernet (wired) with the help of different devices, such as RFID, VR, AR, 3DP, HMD (head mounted device), GPS (global positioning system) and/or smart devices, among others. With this definition, it can be stated that technological investment would be considered unnecessary when I4.0 enablers cannot be implemented together.

Seven reference conceptual frameworks are considered based on I4.0 design principles. They share different principles, namely: interconnection/connectivity, information transparency, decentralised decision making, technical assistance, the human factor, technology, intelligence/awareness, knowledge; interoperability. There is the limitation of confusion which arises given their intrinsic relation to one another.

In the interconnection/connectivity category, the importance of SDN, TSN and 5G/6G technology as potential enablers of rapid connections for the quantity of data generated in I4.0 is highlighted. Mathematical models will also act as integrators of different modelling languages. In this context, heuristic and metaheuristic algorithms were analysed for decentralised decision making based on solving production planning problems with an I4.0 approach. The human factor of I4.0 is considered by many authors in relation to the role that humans will play in future factories, their competences and their integration with CPS. Unqualified jobs have been determined to be more susceptible to be replaced with robots. Hence the human role in I4.0 and the creation of new learning methodologies by incorporating AR will drastically change the education and training of professionals apt to work in an I4.0 setting insofar as the use of VR and its familiarisation must be included in teachings as an essential requirement in the competences that a future professional has to acquire.

Different linear programming models were identified for the reconfigurable production planning of automated flow lines based on I4.0 technologies.

It is worth stressing the difference observed between an IM system, which must be flexible, reconfigurable, low-cost, able to change, agile and adapted, and an SM system, which must know how to best exploit its intelligence capacities and identifying a much more advanced manufacturing system to add the social dimension, SCPS, which makes SM even more superior to conventional IM.

In the smart category, technological enablers, characteristics, key elements, reference architectures and algorithms were dealt with for I4.0 SM decision making (Table 6). SM was identified as the basis for I4.0 and it is commonplace to confuse I4.0 with IM in the literature.

For interoperability, communication is a key factor, and emphasis is placed on 5G technology and a protocol for communication between machines known as OPC UA.

CPS were determined as integrating the physical world with a I4.0 virtual world, and the 5C and 8C architectures are referred to for this purpose. The CPPS concept and its key enabler, gateway was identified. It is worth stressing that real-time research in I4.0 is an aspect that is less featured in the literature.

The DT can enable validating system performance in a semiphysical simulation manner. The DT directly conducts validation and tests that can locate the malfunction and inefficiency reason, rule out design mistakes, and test the practicability of running physical equipment. Different DT definitions and contributions are identified in the literature and its relation to enable a CPS by mirroring the real world with the use of simulation.

OPC UA technology was also taken as a part of the RAMI 4.0 architecture and DDS as part of the IIRA architecture. Both architectures are necessary to supply data in real time in I4.0.

As for technologies that enable I4.0, different enablers exist that have normally been dealt with separately, such as: the decentralised decision-making capacity by means of algorithms, models, heuristics or metaheuristics; cloud manufacturing, which employs a cloud computing network whose platforms (including C2NET) are one of the most relevant parts to outline I4.0; the IoT, which is essential for enabling transformation to I4.0 by supplying intelligence in the products and processes of the whole supply chain; smart devices; AR; VR, which is classified as immersive and semi-immersive; 3DP, which is key in additive manufacturing. Among the advantages of enablers, we found the skill to possess flexibility, self-configuration, self-maintenance, end-to-end integration, information in real time and the human-machine interaction capacity. The disadvantages, or challenges, include communication due to the vast quantity of produced data. Therefore, stable, reliable, secure and swift connections will be necessary. Then there were the challenges linked with workers' competences in an intelligent I4.0 environment, the high costs of changes made to technology, and confusion upon converting I3.0 into I4.0 when only technology changes. Blockchain has been identified as an important technology and many authors highlight its main capability to enable decentralisation using transactions dubbed as smart contracts. The employment of blockchain enables increased security, enhances traceability and reduces costs.

However, the blockchain itself also has security issues and several studies indicate how to incorporate other technologies to enhance the security, transparency, and traceability of blockchain technology.

Different reference architectures and a modelling language were identified for I4.0, namely RAMI 4.0, IIRA, IBM I4.0 and NIST SM for the architectures and I4PML as the modelling language. Moreover, to date, the literature has identified 39 articles that deal with the RAMI 4.0 theme, five that have examined IIRA, one related to IBM I4.0 and one refers to the I4PML modelling language. Other reference architectures were dealt with in this paper and are summarised in Table 9. Different models were also reviewed, which focus on I4.0 production planning. Here the models most frequently dealt with were analytical ones, followed by artificial intelligence and simulation models.

Table 9. Summary of reference I4.0 architectures

Authors	Approach
Shrouf et al. (2014)	Reference architecture for smart factories based on the IoT with an energy efficiency approach
Lee et al. (2015)	5C architecture to integrate CPS into manufacturing
Wan et al. (2016)	Software-defined IIoT architecture for managing physical devices and supplying an interface to exchange information
Thames and Schaefer (2016)	SDCM architecture with which the characteristics of I4.0 systems are to be achieved
Batista et al. (2017)	I4SEA architecture based on information technologies for I4.0.
Chen et al. (2017)	Hierarchical architecture of a I4.0 smart factory
Jiang (2017)	8C architecture to integrate CPS into manufacturing
Molano et al. (2017)	Metamodel to integrate the IoT, social networks and the cloud of I4.0 and an architecture for the IIoT
Cicconi et al. (2017)	CPS simulation model that considers the time and energy use of an LGV and the CPPS architecture
Ma et al. (2017)	A mechanism for the virtualisation of a network of companies based on the IoT and cloud computing by a software-defined integrated system infrastructure
Guo et al. (2017)	The design and architecture of a PON for connecting machines
Guizzi et al. (2017)	Reference architecture for the I4.0 production planning of CPS
Molano et al. (2017)	Metamodel of an architecture for the IIoT based on integrating the IoT, social networks, the cloud and I4.0
Lucas-Estañ et al. (2018)	A software for hierarchical communication and a data management architecture for I4.0
Ahleroff et al. (2021)	Present a DT reference architecture model based on RAMI 4.0

5 Conclusions

This article has offered a literature review about I4.0 by considering technological enablers together and a main production planning approach in the I4.0 context. It is worth highlighting that a considerable number of reference conceptual frameworks were proposed and were the basis to create our own definition of the term I4.0.

The following relevant aspects of I4.0 design were identified: technical assistance, decentralised decision making, interconnection/connectivity, information transparency, intelligence/awareness, knowledge and interoperability. Seven reference conceptual frameworks were identified and compared to propose an I4.0 classification made up of the main categories of: interconnection/connectivity, decentralised decision making, the human factor, intelligence/awareness, interoperability, information transparency, technology, organisation, conceptual frameworks and production planning. The information search strategy considered 130 publications, and the following key words stood out: *big data*, *business*, *decision*, *human*, *smart*, *integration*, *intelligent* and *IoT*, which were always followed by *industry 4.0*. According to Nickerson et al (2013), the proposed classification can help researchers to conceptually or empirically analyse, structure and understand I4.0 complex systems. The classification was based on the following classification criteria: number of citations, enablers considering I4.0 and the novelty of the theme. It has been shown that categories are closely related to one another; for instance, integration refers to CPS, which implies integrating the virtual world with the real world. In the production planning knowledge area, which is interesting for the objectives of the present work, the following problems were contemplated: the design and dynamic programming of services in I4.0 cyber-physical supply networks; production programming by considering reducing energy use; the production planning of a flow shop on a flexible assembly line; the design of automated flow lines (self-configuration and self-organisation) and mass customisation, among others. Finally, future research lines are indicated, which were identified while preparing this state of the art: (1) a conceptual framework that specifically defines what a company must do, more specifically an SME, to move towards I4.0; (2) quantitative models and algorithms that support this conceptual framework and integrate I4.0 characteristics; (3) the optimising and simulation technologies of these models and algorithms; (4) a standardised reference I4.0 architecture; (5) the practical applications of production planning models for the problems of an SOMS by combining I4.0 enablers; (6) validation of the proposed conceptual models and reference architectures found in the literature, like RAMI I4.0.

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